

MOSFET Circuits Demystified

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Abstract

An informal survey was conducted to test our hypothesis that engineering and physics students who have taken courses in Circuit Theory and Analog Electronics are clearly unprepared to design, build, and test basic circuits with MOSFETS. The survey included but was not limited to blogs posted on the internet by hapless students. These students were very familiar with the theoretical underpinnings of MOSFETS including all the relevant equations. The sources from which these students were learning failed to provide even the most rudimentary information that is necessary to build and test the simplest MOSFET circuits. These students were routinely directed to the datasheets of devices. This practice is misguided as we will explain in this paper. This paper was written to provide the guidance to enable these students to confidently design, build, and test simple MOSFET circuits. We explain how to easily design, build, and test two types of constant-current sources and measure device parameters confidently and quickly without getting flustered with datasheets. We also include MOSFET circuits with LEDs, a topic of increasing importance but rarely found in the current literature. Finally, we empower the students by introducing them to an excellent and free simulator to efficiently test their circuits and calculations.

Keywords: *MOSFETS, circuits, design, engineering, physics.*

Introduction

Engineering and Physics students who have taken courses in Circuit Theory and Analog Electronics are clearly unprepared to design, build, and test even the most basic circuits with MOSFETS. These hapless students are known to vent their frustration on internet blogs. These students are thoroughly familiar with the theoretical underpinnings of MOSFETS including all the relevant equations. They can talk the talk of MOSFETS, but they cannot walk the walk of MOSFETS. The sources from which these students are learning failed to provide even the most rudimentary information that is necessary to build and test the simplest MOSFET circuits (Sedra, et al., 2019). These students were routinely directed to the datasheets of devices (Physics Forums, 2011). This practice is misguided as we will explain in this paper. This paper was written to provide the guidance to enable these students to confidently design, build, and test simple MOSFET circuits. We explain by means of examples how to easily design, build, and test two types of constant-current sources and measure device parameters confidently and quickly without getting flustered with datasheets. The secret sauce is to focus on one MOSFET which is best by test and whose device parameters we provide upfront. Once they have built up their confidence, we show a simple circuit to measure the device parameters of any MOSFET. We would still dissuade them from MOSFET-hopping. We would advise them to stick with what is best by test. We also include MOSFET circuits with LEDs, a topic of increasing importance but rarely found in the current literature. Finally,

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Materials and Methods

We will consider a MOSFET constant-current source. Our MOSFET is 2N7000. This MOSFET is best by test. The current is constant at 28.1 mA even when the top resistor changes! We generally do not use an ammeter to measure the current. We measure the voltages and figure out the currents. $I_D = (15 - 14.1)/33 = 27.3$ mA. The discrepancy is simply due to the resistor not being precisely 33Ω . We will use the equation when the MOSFET is in the saturation region. The reason is that in the saturation region $V_{DS} \geq V_{GS}$ which is the case in our three circuits. The threshold voltage $V_t = 1V$. (Later in this paper I will show you how we can easily measure this parameter. Do not rely on the datasheet). The MOSFET equation for the saturation region is

$$I_D = \frac{1}{2} k (V_{GS} - V_t)^2 \quad (1)$$

Let us use this equation to solve for k. Note that $V_{GS} = 5 - 2.81 = 2.19$

$$28.1 = \frac{1}{2} k (2.19 - 1)^2$$

$$k = 40 \text{ mA/V}^2 \quad (2)$$

Now you know how easy it is to experimentally determine k. It is misguided to try to find k from the datasheet or rely on AI (Reddit., n.d.)!

Figure 1. MOSFET Constant Current Source

Let us consider another design for a MOSFET constant-current source. (Figure 2)

$$I_D = \frac{1}{2} k (V_{GS} - V_t)^2$$

$$I_D = \frac{1}{2} (40) (2 - 1)^2$$

$$I_D = 20 \text{ mA}$$

Figure 2. Another MOSFET Constant Current Source and 2N7000 Pinout

The experimental determination of the threshold voltage V_t is exceedingly simple from the circuit in Figure 2. Tweak the $2\text{k}\Omega$ resistor to reduce 2V to 1V . The current will decrease from 20 mA to 0 mA . Remember we do not use an ammeter! The 3V will creep up to 5V . Then you will know that the current is zero and $V_{GS} = V_t$.

We will now consider a MOSFET circuit to drive a green LED that has a nominal drop of 3V across it and draws a nominal current of 20 mA . You do not need a data sheet because the label on the packet clearly states this. Do not use a yellow LED that drops 2V in this circuit. Suffice it to say that bad things can happen! Let us calculate the expected current through the LED. By observation, $V_{DS} = V_{GS}$ which means the MOSFET is operating in the saturation region.

$$I_D = \frac{1}{2} k (V_{GS} - V_t)^2$$

$$I_D = \frac{1}{2} (40) (1.95 - 1)^2$$

$$I_D = 18 \text{ mA}$$

Finally, I would like to empower the reader by introducing you to an excellent free simulator to efficiently test your circuits and calculations. It is called EveryCircuit (n.d.). Select the MOSFET and the wrench tool to set $V_{TO} = 1\text{V}$, $KP = 8 \text{ mA/V}^2$ to get $K = 40 \text{ mA/V}^2$. Note that $K = KP (W/L)$ and the default value of $W/L = 5$. Also set $LAMBDA = 0$.

Figure 3 MOSFET Driving a green LED

Results

We obtained excellent results that exceeded our expectations. We developed expertise in MOSFET circuit design. We analyzed two types of constant-current sources. The first one taught us an easy means of calculating the MOSFET parameter k . We found that the 2N7000 has $k = 40 \text{ mA/V}^2$. The second circuit allowed us to quickly determine another MOSFET parameter V_t . We found that the 2N7000 has $V_t = 1\text{V}$. Then we designed, built, and tested a circuit to drive a green LED with the 2N7000 MOSFET. Finally, we learned about an excellent free simulator to efficiently test our MOSFET circuits and save time on calculations.

Discussion

We wrote this paper to help students master the design of simple MOSFET circuits. It was prompted by an informal survey that showed that engineering and physics students who have taken courses in Circuit Theory and Analog Electronics are clearly unprepared to design, build, and test basic circuits with MOSFETS. These students were very familiar with the theoretical underpinnings of MOSFETS including all the relevant equations. The sources from which these students were learning failed to provide even the most rudimentary information that is necessary to build and test the simplest MOSFET circuits (Sedra, et al., 2019). These students were routinely directed to the datasheets of devices (Physics Forums, 2011; Reddit, n.d.). This practice is misguided as we explained in this paper. This paper was written to provide the guidance to enable these students to confidently design, build, and test simple MOSFET circuits. We explained how to easily design, build, and test two types of constant-current sources and measure device parameters confidently and quickly without getting flustered with datasheets. We also included MOSFET circuits with LEDs, a topic of increasing importance but rarely found in the current literature. Finally, we empowered the students by introducing them to an excellent free simulator (EveryCircuit, n.d.) to efficiently test their circuits and calculations.

Conclusions

We concluded that pedagogically best practices must be followed if we want our engineering and physics students to master the experimental aspects. These students were very familiar with the theoretical underpinnings of MOSFETS including all the relevant equations. However, the instruction failed to provide even the most rudimentary information that is necessary to build and test the simplest MOSFET circuits. These students were routinely directed to the datasheets of devices. This practice is misguided as we explained in this paper. This paper was written to provide the guidance to enable these students to confidently design, build, and test simple MOSFET circuits. We explained how to easily design, build, and test two types of constant-current sources and measure device parameters confidently and quickly without getting flustered with datasheets. We also included MOSFET circuits with LEDs, a topic of increasing importance but rarely found in the current literature. Finally, we empowered the students by introducing them to an excellent and free simulator to efficiently test their circuits and calculations.

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